

UC_UHI Graz

Technical Report on airborne and satellite thermal images comparison

Input data:

- Thermal satellite images by Landsat 8, thermal band, on the city of Graz. Time series from 2013 to 2021, GSD 30 m
- Land Surface Temperature images estimated from aerial thermal images acquired in September 2021, GSD 50 cm
- Surface material map derived from the classification of hyperspectral aerial images, GSD 2 m

Results analysis:

In Figure 1 is represented the Land Surface Temperature (LST) retrieved from airborne and satellite sensors over the city of Graz. Upon the visual comparison of the LST, it appears clear how the detailed thermal signature of the city is identified well by the airborne sensor meanwhile the satellite sensor is capable to capture the macroscopic distribution of temperature across the city identifying the vegetation, the river Mur that divide the city of Graz as well as some hot spots at the rail freight yard and at the industrial district.

Figure 1. Land surface temperature over Graz: a) LST derived from airborne sensor at 0.5 m resolution on the 9/9/2021; b) LST derived from Landsat 8 scene at 30m resolution on the 12/09/2021.

Figure 2 presents a detailed view of the airborne-satellite LST difference over an AOI at the center of Graz. Figure 2a, with 30m pixel size, clearly shows the difficulty at satellite resolution to resolve for single houses, squares or neighborhoods as well due to its low resolution. Figure 2b, with 0.5m pixel size, exemplifies the quality of airborne derived LST in the urban context, the vegetated areas appear to be in more agreement with the satellite measurements (i.e. white pixels with near zero values) compared to some buildings rooftops. This can be explained by both the higher resolution of the sensor itself (i.e. reducing the pixel mixing effect) as well as for the detailed emissivity map used to recover the LST at ground level from the airborne sensor.

Figure 2. Airborne-Satellite LST difference detailed view over an AOI in Graz. a) the difference is calculated at the 30m resolution of the satellite. b) difference calculated at 0.5m resolution of the airborne thermal flight.

To quantify the temperature difference between the satellite and airborne sensors a resampling of the satellite LST has been performed via nearest-neighbor then Airborne-Satellite LST pixel wise differences have been aggregated over continuous and homogeneous land cover classes as reported in Figure 3. Besides the difference in magnitude between the two sensors, higher temperatures are measured from the airplane thanks to the higher resolution that sharply reduces the pixel mixing. For the vegetated areas (latest 3 classes) the difference is smaller. This is confirmed both pixel wise as shown in Figure 2b as well as for the entire city area of Graz due to the presence of large vegetated areas both within and at the outskirts of the city (Figure 1).

Figure 3. Airborne-satellite LST difference median aggregated over continuous and homogeneous land cover classes.

Table 1. Sensors with thermal imaging capabilities at different scales and frequency

Platform	Sensor	Spatial Resolution	# Thermal bands	Thermal range [um]	Revisit time	Ref
Sentinel-3 (A&B)	SLSTR	1 km	3	3.7-12.0	~1 day	link
Terra & Aqua	MODIS	1 km	16	3.6-14.4	1 day	link
Landsat (8&9)	TIRS	100 m	2	10.0-12.5	8 days	link
ISS	ECOSTRESS	70 m	5	8.0-12.7	~4 days (on-demand)	link
HotSat-1	MWIR	3.5 m	1	3.7-5.0	on-demand	link
Airplane	DualDigiTHE RM by IGI	0.5-1 m	1	7.5-14.0	on-demand	link

Drone	Zenmuse H20T	0.1-0.2m	1	8.0-14.0	on-demand	link
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Time Series of LST ground corrected from Landsat mission

At this WMS end points you will find the data described [here](#):

<https://usage.geocat.live/mapping/ows?service=WMS&version=1.1.1&request=GetCapabilities>

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_4

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_5

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_6

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_7

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_8

Graz_FBK_LST_hot_spots:hot_spots_month_9

2013-2023 Monthly Median LST over Graz

April

May

June

July

August

September

288 K

325 K